

Review of soft computing models in design and control of rotating electrical machines

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Abstract: Rotating electrical machines are the electromechanical energy convertors with a fundamental impact on the production and conversion of energy. Novelty and advancement in the control and high-performance design of these machines are of interests in energy management. Soft computing methods are known as important tools that significantly improve the performance of rotating electrical machines in both aspects of control and design. From this perspective, a wide range of energy management systems are highly relying on the advancement of soft computing techniques used for rotating electrical machines. This article presents the state of the art of soft computing techniques and their applications that have greatly influenced and contributed to the advancement of this important realm of energy. Through a novel taxonomy of techniques and applications the most important advancements in the field are reviewed for providing an insight into the future of control and design of rotating electrical machines.

Keywords: soft computing techniques; artificial intelligence; machine learning; rotating electrical machines; energy systems; electrical machines; hybrid models; ensemble models; energy informatics; electrical engineering; data science; energy management

Acronyms used frequently in this work

RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error	DL	Deep Learning
RBF	Radial Basis Function	ML	Machine Learning
SVM	Support Vector Machine	SC	Soft Computing
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System	MAE	Mean Absolut Error
ANN	Artificial Neural Network	MPE	Mean Percentage Error
MLP	Multi Layered Perceptron	PM	Permanent Magnet
GRNN	Generalized Regression Neural Networks	MIC	Multi-Functional Intelligent Controller
VEH	Vibration Energy Harvester	IPMSM	Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization	MMO	Multi-Model Or Multi-Modal Optimization
MWT	Multi Ripple Remodel	ABC	Artificial Bee Colony
DSIM	Dual Star Induction Machine	DWT	Discrete Wavelet Transform
DG	Distributed Generation	MGA	Modified Genetic Algorithm
IM	Induction Machine	DGA	Dissolved Gas Analysis
CCGT	Combined Cycle Gas Turbine	DFIM	Double Fed Induction Machine
DC	Direct Current	AFPMSG	axial flux permanent magnet synchronous generator
ANN-SMC	Artificial Neural Networks - sliding mode control	EC	Evolutionary Computation
SA	Simulated Annealing	FE	Finite-element
GA	Genetic Algorithm	DE	Differential Evolution
AS	Ant System	SPSRM	Single-Phase Switched Reluctance Machine
PMSG	Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator	SNC	static nonlinear controller
FR	Feeder Reconfiguration	ABC	Artificial Bee Colony
PID	Proportional Integral Derivative	RBFNN	Radial Basis Function Neural Network
TPLI	Total Power Loss Index	TVPI	Total Voltage profile Index

1. Introduction

In 1831 Michael Faraday has invented the disk machine which can be considered as the first true DC machine. Until 1870 when Thomas Edison has started the commercial development of the DC generator, electrical machines were applied and investigated only in laboratories. Edison's pioneering concept of electric power distribution from central generation stations allowed the introduction of the electric grid infrastructure concept, which was the primary condition for widespread the application of electric motors [1]. The patent of the three-phase induction motor by Nikola Tesla in 1888 was an utmost important milestone in the history of the electric machines. After that, the construction of electrification began, which lasted until 1930 in the USA, and then conquered

worldwide [2]. Nowadays, it is estimated that more than sixty-five percent of the energy demand of present-day industrialized countries used by electrical drives [3]. Constant or variable speed or servo-motor drives are employed almost everywhere: in households, industry, electric traction, transportation, aerospace, military equipment, medical equipment and agriculture, etc. These sectors are mainly focused on an alternative source for the existing power transfer technologies, where major subsystems would also be controlled and driven electronically [4].

Recently, electromechanical drives for position and speed control play a key role in processes control, electric vehicles, factory automation, robotics and energy conservation. Due to the introduction of vector control methods in the 1970s and low price and the high reliability of cage induction motors made induction motor as the most popular rotating electrical machine. The recent advancements of PM materials, solid-state devices and microelectronics have contributed to new energy efficient, high performance electric drives which use modern PM brushless motors [5-8]. It is quite possible that, these permanent magnet brushless motor drives will become predominant in the next century [9].

Nevertheless, the control, design and optimization of rotating electrical machines require advanced techniques and modern mathematical models to keep up with the ever increasing demand for energy [10-14]. In fact, the practical solutions of engineering problems involve model-integrated computing [15, 16]. Model-based computing approaches or in other word Soft Computing provide a challenging way to replace the procedure with a knowledge-based method [17]. The Soft Computing (SC) techniques denote a set of computational approaches that are used to approximate mathematical problems which are hard or unable to solve by time-consuming classical mathematical tools. Combining SC, non-conventional and novel data representation techniques is a possible way to overcome this difficulty [18-21]. Over the last decades, the benefits of SC techniques have been widely recognized and has brought several new solutions in the design and control of electrical machines [22, 23]. However, there is a gap in the effectiveness of the SC models [24, 25]. Thus, identification and evaluation of the SC models would be an effective approach to evaluate the progress and provide an insight into the future application of SC methods [26, 27]. Consequently, the intention of current work is to give a comprehensive overview on the recent state-of-the-art solutions using soft computing techniques in design and control of rotating electrical machines.

The organization of rest of this article is as follow. In section two the research methodology of the review is presented. Section three presents the review of the SC models used in electrical rotating machines. Section four presents the discussion followed by section five with a conclusion to the review.

2. Methodology

The primary goal of this survey is to present the state of the art of SC techniques in design and control of rotating electrical machines. The purpose of the research methodology is to identify, classify and review the notable peer-reviewed articles concerned in top-level subject fields. In our comprehensive review using the Thomson Reuters Web-of-Science and Elsevier Scopus for implementation of the search queries would assure that any paper in database would meet the essential quality measures, originality, high impact and high h-index.

To identify the application of soft computing in design, control and development of rotating electrical machines the search queries are to be carefully chosen to build the initial database. The taxonomy of SC influences the search queries. Figure 1 presents the principal SC tools and their subsections that we have identified by a slight modifications of the classifications given in [27-28]. Accordingly, the keywords of the search queries to identify the SC tools are selected to be "fuzzy" or "neural network" or "evolutionary computation" or "genetic" or "meta-heuristics" or "ant colony" or "particle swarm" or "tabu search" or "cuckoo search" or "simulated annealing" or "Bayesian network" or "Markov logic network" or "rough set".

Figure 1. taxonomy of soft computing methods used in making the initial database based on [28, 29]

On the other hand the search queries for the applications to rotating electrical machines may include various aspects of design and control i.e. electric machine, rotating electrical machine, electric motor, electric generator, electromechanical generator, transformer and electrostatic, homopolar, permanent, brushed, magnet, reluctance and induction machines. Consequently, the entire search query is presented as: (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("electric machine" OR "rotating electrical machine" OR "electric motor" OR "electric generator" OR "electromechanical energy converter" OR "generator" OR "Transformer" OR "Brushed machine" OR "Permanent magnet machine" OR "Induction machine") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Reluctance machine" OR "Electrostatic machine" OR "Homopolar machine") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("fuzzy" OR "neural network" OR "evolutionary computation" OR "genetic" OR "metaheuristics" OR "ant colony" OR "particle swarm" OR "tabu search" OR "cuckoo search" OR "simulated annealing" OR "bayesian network" OR "Markov logic network" OR "rough set")) AND PUBYEAR > 1986 AND PUBYEAR < 2018. This query results a total of 24,382 documents. It should be noted that each section contains a brief result and conclusion about the subject to help the authors and researchers for sustainable and suitable decision about applications of soft-computing techniques.

Furthermore, to present an in-depth review and understanding of each modeling technique and its progress we aimed at having different categories for the SC models used i.e. Simple Fuzzy Systems, ANFIS: Neuro-fuzzy, Advanced ANFIS/Neuro-fuzzy: hybrids, Neural Computing: ANN, EC and Metaheuristics, Ant colony, Tabu and Cuckoo search, Simulated annealing, Probabilistic reasoning and Bayesian Networks, and Hybrid soft computing methods. Furthermore, the research methodology follows a comprehensive and structured workflow based on a systematic database search and cross-reference snowballing. The flowchart of the research methodology is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2. Methodology of research

In the step1 of the methodology the initial database of the relevant articles is identified based on the search queries of SC models through exploring the Thomson Reuters Web-of-Science and Elsevier Scopus databases. In step2 the database is created with the relevant literature. For every SC model we applied a new search query to well suit that search. Nevertheless, a number of articles in the initial database might not be highly suitable for the review. For that matter the step3 investigates an indent consideration of the literature to pass the irrelevant papers to the step4 to be excluded from the database. Note that, the search queries will identify the relevant articles yet the queries are uncertain whether the SC model belong to a hybrid category. For instance a hybrid model of SC may include single SC model. Therefore, step5 is designed to reclassify the literature into one of the categories of SC models.

3. State of the Art of Soft Computing Techniques and Applications

Exploring the number of literatures on rotating electrical machines shows a continued progress on the design and advancement of rotating electrical machines. Almost half a million documents on this particular realm shows the importance of this topic and the dependent technologies. Figure 3 shows the progress in number of literature. It is also apparent that the use of SC models has been started from late 80s and early 90s and boosted the design advancement.

Figure 3. Number of published literatures on rotating electrical machines from 1963-2017: 483,320 document results. (Source: Scopus & Web of Science)

Exploring the various SC models in a wide applications to design and controlling the rotating electrical machines results an extended database. The literature has been progressing since early 80s with a fast paste of involvement of SC methods in design and control purposes. Figure 4 shows the increasing popularity of SC especially during the past two decades. It is apparent that statistics on the number of literature change when using soft computing for the advancement. Furthermore the primary analysis the database of search shows that some SC methods have been more popular that the others and the usage of many SC methods has been very limited and not worth mentioning in the review. The most popular SC methods can be classified in five categories of Fuzzy Systems, Neural Computing: ANN, EC and Metaheuristics, Probabilistic reasoning and Bayesian Networks, and further Hybrid soft computing methods.

Figure 4. Analysis of the literature on soft computing in design, control and development of rotating electrical machines from 1987-2017. Total of 30,382 document results. (Source: Scopus & Web of Science)

The analysis of literature type shows a major number of articles are original papers written on the advancement and development of rotating electrical machine and only a tiny fracture of literature is devoted to review papers (see, Figs. 2-5).

Figure 5. Analysis of the literature by based on countries (Source: Scopus & Web of Science)

Analysis of the literature by based on countries shows that China, USA, India, Iran, and UK are among the top five active regions on the advancement of rotating electrical machines using SC methods (see, Figs. 6). 1987-2017 (Source: Scopus)

Figure 6. Analysis of the literature based on publishing sources (Source: Scopus & Web of Science)

The top five source includes: Proceedings Of SPIE The International Society For Optical Engineering 5841 Lecture Notes In Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes In Artificial Intelligence And Lecture Notes In Bioinformatics 4064 IEEE Transactions On Magnetics 3989 IEEE Transactions On Industry Applications 3306 Conference Record IAS Annual Meeting IEEE Industry Applications Society 2943, from a total of Total of 24,382 document results (see, Figs. 6).. 1987-2017 (Source: Scopus)

Figure 7. Literature type on the on rotating electrical machines using soft computing, from 1987-2017. (Source: Scopus & Web of Science)

The analysis of literature type shows a major number of articles are original papers written on the advancement and development of rotating electrical machine and only a tiny fracture of literature is devoted to review papers (see, Figs. 7-8)..

Figure 8. Subject area of rotating electrical machines using soft computing, from 1987-2017. The math, computer science, and energy has a rise (Source: Scopus & Web of Science)

3.1 Fuzzy Systems

Fuzzy logic is widely used for modeling complex and ill-defined systems. The core concept relies on the application of linguistic variables which are transformed into graded membership functions. Therefore, fuzzy logic is an extension of classical Boolean logic where logical statements are not only true or false but can also range from almost certain to very unlikely. A large number of practical applications apply fuzzy logic due to its excellent approximation properties.

3.1.1 Simple Fuzzy Systems

Fuzzy logic is widely used in nonlinear controllers due to their easy applicability and high performance. These are capable of replacing the most common Lyapunov's second method of nonlinear control, which is a complicated technique from mathematical point of view and needs very skilled designers. The most widely known two the Mamdani- and Sugeno- type inference systems. The main difference between them is that the latter allows functions as output instead of membership functions. Fuzzy logic serves as useful tools for engineering practice; a numerous examples found for the utilization of fuzzy logic in the control and design of electrical machines. Major works from the recent past collected in Table 1 illustrate that this trend is still unbroken.

Table 1. Simple fuzzy systems in rotating electrical machine

Reference	year	SC method	Application
Aguilar et al. [30]	2017	Fuzzy logic	brake control
C. S.; Rao Amulya, M. S. [31]	2016	Mamdani type inference	Fault detection by the investigation of vibration data
M.; Sakly Ben Smida, A. [32]	2016	Fuzzy controller	power regulation
Z. Husain [33]	2018	Fuzzy expert system	condition monitoring of power transformers via dissolved gas analysis test
S.; Sedraoui Kahla, M.; Bechouat, M.; Soufi, Y. [34]	2018	combination of standard on-off strategy with fuzzy logic	maximize the power point tracking of wind energy

Aguilar [30] used a simple fuzzy logic algorithm for the intelligent brake control of an electric motorcycles engine in order to recover the maximum energy in braking processes while maintaining the vehicle's stability. The success of the employed method is very bold, such that the results of comparing regenerative system with the ABS in a low adhesion condition have been presented in Fig. 12 in terms of Mean deceleration (a) and Distance (b). Based on results, the proposed systems could optimize the energy regeneration strategy.

Fig. 12. results of the study by Aguilar [30] in terms of Mean deceleration (a) and Distance (b)

In paper Amulya (2016) [31] a steam turbo generator condition assessment problem is considered in which the condition is determined by a fuzzy logic-based vibration analysis. Recommendations for improving the performance of the conventional pitch angle control strategy for power regulation in wind turbines is given in Ben Smida (2016) [32] in which the pitch angle is based on fuzzy logic. The study was developed using fuzzy logic and PID controllers. The comparison of the performance of two systems was performed using MAE and MPE. Such that, fuzzy logic controller with low MAE (29.02%) and MPE (0.0088%) values provided a best controlling ability compared that for PID controller which can make a smooth controlling process.

Husain (2018) [33] applies a fuzzy expert system for fault diagnosis of power systems which incorporates the information obtained from dissolved gas analysis test. The proposed approach could successfully reduce the issues raised by the conventional fault diagnosis methods. Also, the proposed method by Arumugom 2017 improves dynamic response and the energy saving and by the fast detection ability and removes the errors raised by the DVR response.

Kahla (2018) [34] introduces a fuzzy logic system in the on-off control strategy in case of wind energy conversion. The proposed method allows maximizing the power point tracking of wind energy and reducing the mechanical loads in comparison to the standard on-off control strategy.

3.1.2 ANFIS: Neuro-fuzzy

Artificial neural systems represent systems acting as parallel distributed computing networks. Neural systems is able to find new associations, new functional dependencies and new patterns through learning therefore their primary advantage is their additivity. Consequently, combining the neural networks with fuzzy logic techniques is clearly useful; the nice approximation properties are complemented with higher additivity and parallelism. The such composed system is called fuzzy neural, neural fuzzy, neuro-fuzzy or fuzzy-neuro network, or ANFIS in which for instance neural networks can be used to tune membership functions of fuzzy systems. Its applicability is supported by a vast amount of published papers. However, in electrical machine design issues only few examples are found.

Table 2. Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Systems in Electrical Machines

Reference	Year	Method	Application
Arumugom [35]	2017	ANFIS based MIC controller	Dynamic Voltage Restorer Controller
Aruna [36]	2016	MWT and Accommodative ANFIS with ABC algorithmic rule.	IPMSM control
Bentouhami [37]	2016	Neuro-fuzzy combined method	Control of DSIM
Haritha [38]	2017	Q learning and ANFIS	Optimal relationship of rotor speed of the PMSG
Thankachan and Singh [39]	2016	Neuro-fuzzy	speed and torque control of Induction Machine (IM) drive

An interesting application of neuro-fuzzy systems is described in Arumugom (2017) [35] where the authors make an attempt is made to design Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) with energy conservation using MIC and VEH. Aruna (2016) [36] proposed a hybrid method using ANFIS for the speed control of IPMSM. Their results demonstrate that their solution enables better disturbance rejection compared to the classic PID controller. The settling, arising and overshooting times of the proposed controlling method has been compared with PID, MR-PID and MWNN-PSO controlling algorithms. Fig. 13 indicates the time values for each terms. The related results indicate the proposed controlling method is the best technique to eliminate the nonlinearity with a high reliability, and sustainable performance compared with that for the other techniques.

Fig. 13. Comparing the time values for the study by Aruna (2016) [36]

Advanced method for the control of DSIM supplied by Five-Level Inverter is shown by Bentouhami (2016) [37] who apply ANFIS controller composed of an on-line learning algorithm with a neuro-fuzzy network. Haritha (2017) [38] introduced a neuro fuzzy and Q learning –based technique for the maximum power point tracking control for improving learning efficiency of PMSG wind energy conversion system (WECS).

3.1.3 Advanced ANFIS/Neuro-fuzzy: hybrids

Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference systems can be supported or combined further mathematical tools if the problem requires. The resulted systems are called hybrid fuzzy-neuro systems. In advanced ANFIS systems the capabilities of the neural network are higher due to better learning algorithms (for e.g. Trust Region Reflective) so they are able to learn various parameters. These techniques are especially useful in highly nonlinear control problems of electrical machines or in condition assessment issues-

Table 3 Hybrid Techniques applied in electrical machine design and control.

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Li et al (2005) [40]	2005	robust model reference fuzzy controller	DC servo motor system
Fatih Kececioglu [41]	2017	neuro-fuzzy controller (NFC)	hybrid passive filter configuration proposed for PWM rectifiers
Gnanaprakasam [42]	2015	combination of S-transformation algorithm & ANFIS	detecting and classifying the vibration signal of IM
Hossain [43]	2015	FLC, SNC & ANFIS	Nonlinear controllers augment of a large-scale hybrid power system
Dehghani et al. [21]		ANFIS and Grey Wolf	Hydropower generator performance

A vast amount of literature on nonlinear control solutions have been publish in recent years. For instance, Li et al (2005) [40] propose a control technique using a robust model reference controller with the combination of hybrid fuzzy controller. The core of the control strategy is based on the classical Lyapunov technique which is a complicated technique, but the control signal includes fuzzy, classic and robust terms. Fuzzy logic controller was compared with hybrid-fuzzy controller using RMSE values in terms of Output tracking for dc servo motor and inverted pendulum. The results have been presented in Fig. 14. Based on results the hybrid controlling method have the best performance in both terms.

Fig. 14. Results for the study by Li et al (2005) [40]

In order to limit the current and voltage harmonics, and to improve total harmonic distortion and true power factor in Fatih Kececioglu, (2017) [41] a neuro-fuzzy controller is applied in a hybrid passive filter for PWM rectifiers. Gnanaprakasam (2015) [42] proposes a hybrid approach for the detecting and classification of the vibration signal of induction motor in which the fault detection process including the extraction of significant features of vibration signals is carried out by using the S-transformation algorithm. After, the ANFIS classification technique is employed to classify the signal into its faulty or the normal state. S-transform-ANFIS, S-transform-RBFNN, S-transform-FFNN and DWT-RBFNN were compared in terms of accuracy, sensitivity and specificity for IR faulty condition, Centered OR fault, Opposite OR fault, Orthogonal OR fault and BB fault conditions. The general results have been presented in Fig. 15. In all conditions, S-transform-ANFIS has the highest accuracy, sensitivity and specificity compared with those for the other methods.

Fig. 15. Results for the study by Gnanaprakasam (2015) [42]

In paper Hossain (2015) [43] three nonlinear control strategies are compared, namely the FLC, SNC and ANFIS-based controller. Their results show that the proposed FLC-, SNC-, or ANFIS-based VR-FCL are effective in improving the transient stability of a large-scale hybrid power system consisting of a doubly fed induction generator (DFIG)-based wind farm, a photovoltaic (PV) plant, and a synchronous generator (SG).

In general, in all cases mentioned by fuzzy systems, the fuzzy controller has a robust and smooth controlling process, which improves the control process and causes less damage to the hardware used and reduces the cost of servicing and maintaining of the systems. On the other hand, this would have a direct impact on the energy consumption of the control system and would lead to more sustainable control in the control system. This conclusion has also been confirmed in a study by Ardabili et al (2016) [44] to design a fuzzy control system in a Mushroom growing hall. In addition, the operator's dominance and focus also increases with the use of fuzzy systems. Hyphenation hybrid systems can also optimize the system with the benefits of both fuzzy and neural systems in parallel with the creation of a fuzzy control sustainable system.

3.2 Neural Computing

The concept of Neural Networks is usually employed in itself. As the literature review reveals (see, Table 4.) ANNs are a common tool of control tasks of electrical machines as other engineering applications [45, 46]. However, it seems that the abilities of the nets have not yet been exploited in the field of machine design.

Table 4. Artificial Neural Networks

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Bouchiba [47]	2017	ANN-SMC	control of multi motor system consisting of three mechanically coupled induction motors
Çelik et al [48]	2017	multi-layer feedforward ANN	estimate the output power and efficiency of AFPMSG
Zemmit et al [49]	2016	ANN controller	direct torque control of DFIM
Zouggar et al [50]	2018	ANN	voltage and frequency control of a self-excited induction generator

Considering the ANNs-based solutions in the field of electrical machines the study of Bouchiba (2017) [47] provides a fresh example of the NN sliding mode controller for the control for multi-machine web winding systems. The advantage of this technique is that it can significantly reduce the chattering phenomenon and improve the error performance. In this study the simulation and evaluation processes were performed by employing MATLAB/SIMULINK software. Based on results, ANN-SMC controller has ignored the effect of disturbance. On the other hand it is clear that,

the application of a hybrid PI-SMC controller is easy, but the performance of ANN-SMC controller is better than that for the PI-SMC. Detailed results indicate that the net performance improvement and the robustness of ANN-SMC controller are also strong superiority points compared with PI controller. Çelik et al (2017) [48] designed a feed-forward multilayer NN in order to predict the efficiency and output power of an axial flux permanent magnet synchronous generator. Their tests has shown that the NN is highly suitable for this purpose according to the obtained 3% and 4% error percentages. The efficiency and power of a magnet generator were estimated using neural network method. Based on results, the best structure was 2-18-12-2 which generated a maximum error of 3.587% for power and -3.909 for efficiencies value. Also, NN controller could estimate the power values higher than that for the experimental limits, and it can be a suitable technique. A number of modification and improvements proposed for the classical Direct Torque Controller, e.g., Zemmit et al (2016) [50] designed an ANN-DTC controller in which the IP and switching table have been replaced by new Artificial Neural Network. This strategy can reduce the high torque and flux ripples. The paper of Zidani (2018) presents a voltage and frequency control technique of self-excited induction generators that applies a NN –based inverse dynamic model of the system. Results indicate that the proposed technique can significantly increase the performance and stabilize the SEIG's terminal voltage. This can be an economical and efficient way for stabilizing the voltage and also it can be used by DSP or FPGA controller cards on a real-time benchmark system.

In general, according to the results of the papers developed by NN techniques, it can be seen that this method has the most predictive effect on simulations and can therefore affect the performance of the system. Therefore, this system can be modeled from empirical data and based on the behavior of the predictive functional system, and the user's tastes can have the least interference, unlike the fuzzy system. Also, all studies have been conducted in order to improve existing conditions and offer the proposed system the best performance compared to previous systems.

3.3 EC and Metaheuristics

Metaheuristics are computational methods which optimize problems by iteratively making efforts to refine the function of possible solution(s) to achieve a measurement value while guaranteeing polynomial time in spite of brute force optimization methods. The set of metaheuristics contain various algorithms, such as Ant Colony, Evolutionary Optimization, Genetic Algorithms, etc. EC is a subset of metaheuristics which involve algorithms or global optimization inspired by biological evolution. In EC methods is a stochastic optimization method in which the initial set of candidate solutions are generated randomly. After, the new generations (new sets of possible solutions) are iteratively updated while mitigation the natural selection, mutation, etc. The fitting of a candidate solution is determined by a measure defined for the task under examination.

Optimization problems, especially ill-posed or multi objective optimization tasks are common in the control and design problems in most of engineering are including electrical machine and drive systems. Most of the applications found in the latest paper employ the evolutionary computing techniques in nonlinear control tasks. There are only a limited number discussing the application or novelty of EC in rotating electrical machine design.

Table 5. Evolutionary Computing and Metaheuristics

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Mamede [51]	2018	GA and DE	optimum design of SPSRM
Tamilselvi [52]	2018	Adaptive DE algorithm involving dynamic variation of the mutation factor, combined with FE	design of permanent-magnet motors (PMMs) for electric vehicle (EV) applications with multiple operating points
Vanchinathan [53]	2018	Bat Algorithm (BA)	parameter tuning of fractional order PID controller
Virtic [54]	2016	genetic algorithm and an analytical evaluation of objective functions	design optimization of an axial flux permanent magnet synchronous machine with a coreless stator and double external rotor

Design issues of electrical machines are usually raise complicated or multi-objective, ill-defined optimization problems. The application of Evolutionary-based solution or stochastic optimization methods can handle these problems by reducing the computational costs and simultaneously providing near-optimal solutions. For instance, Mamede (2018) [51] presents the combination of GA and DE techniques that allows maximizing the average torque and torque density, and minimizing copper loss of SPSRM. S. B. Tamilselvi, S. (2018) [52] proposes an evolutionary optimization procedure for the design of two, namely the surface-mounted and interior mounted permanent-magnet motor (PMMs) configurations using differential evolution (DE) algorithm. Optimization tasks are the core of most control problems also. The metaheuristic optimization methods are effective alternatives in such cases, especially in sensorless drives. Vanchinathan (2018) [53] introduce the Bat algorithm in the parameter tuning issue of a fractional –order PID controller for speed control of sensorless control of BLDC motors. MGA, ABC and BA methods were employed in FOPID controller in three loads (0, 50 and 100 % of full load) and the simulation was performed using Matlab/Simulink software. Based on results, the proposed BA method, have the lowest steady state error (%), peak time (s), rise time (s) and settling time (s) compared with those for the other methods in each load, separately (Fig. 16). It seems that, BA method have the best performance at 100% in case of settling, rise and peak times but in case of steady state error, the condition of 0% provides the best performance for BA technique. The detailed results have been presented in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16. Results for the study by Vanchinathan (2018) [53]

Finding of Virtic (2016) [54] also support that the evolutionary optimization with the analytical evaluation of objective functions significantly shortens the computational time required for design optimization in comparison with the finite element methods (FEM).

Considering the reasonable and suitable capabilities of the proposed method, it can be concluded that this method is considered as a process optimizer and according to its performance, it is suggested that the hybrid methods in this field can also be developed by researchers.

3.3.1 Ant colony

The Ant Colony System is a search metaheuristic which concept is based on the imitation of ants seeking nutrition. Ants can communicate with each other by sophisticated way, since they mark the different pathways from the anthill to the food sources and back by pheromone hormone respectively. The pheromone paths are perceived by other ant, and most likely to follow. Pathways to foods can be very different, as well as obstacles between them. Ants tend to collect as much food as possible. The characteristics of some individuals are different, but the unity of the colony is very effective. Each ant moves isolated and randomly, but recognizing it pathways marked with pheromone are also likely to follow. Meanwhile increase their pheromone concentration by pheromone emissions, thereby increasing the concentration of the pheromone attractiveness. Thus, the frequencies of frequently used routes increase the pheromone's level while being neglected paths. The pheromone emitted by the ants continuously vaporizes, that is, confirmation on the given route (releasing a new pheromone dose) without decreasing the pheromone level (until contains pheromone). In the event that there are two paths leading to food, the shorter route is more likely to turn the ants (as they arrive sooner and later back). Thus, they often reinforce the pheromone level, thereby providing higher "attractiveness" for the route. But this will attract more ants to the shorter journey. After a while, the shorter this problem. After a while, the shorter way will take most ant while the longer path for pheromone levels will decrease to a minimum level. The Ant Colony metaheuristic shares the search task between the ant agents. These agents have very basic subtleties and, to a certain extent, simulate the behavior of true ants. "Artificial ants" (agents) build on solutions

based on appropriate problem-specific constructive heuristics. The order of the building blocks of the solution used to construct good solutions is determined by a pheromone matrix. The values stored in the pheromone matrix are taken into account by the other agents on a probability basis when constructing his own solutions. The first Ant Colony algorithm was applied for the travelling salesman problem (TSP). Since then, it has been widespread in engineering practice.

Table 6 Application of Ant Colony in electrical machines

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Ameli et al [55]	2017	--	simultaneous dynamic scheduling of feeder reconfiguration and Capacitor Banks switching in the presence of DG units having uncertain and variant generations
Batista et al [56]	2014	AS algorithm on graph	interior permanent magnet motor design

Ameli (2017) [55] applies the Ant Colony algorithm in distribution systems where FR can lead to loss reduction, reliability. Therefore, the purpose of their method is to minimize the total operational cost of the grid and to reduce the costs and losses. Based on Fig. 17, the proposed method strongly reduces the network power losses (DG MW) for both TVPI and TPLI of the DG units.

Fig. 17. Results for the study by Ameli (2017) [55]

Batista (2014) [56] gives a novel solution where the interior permanent magnet motor design domain is discretized into a suitable equivalent graph representation and an Ant System (AS) algorithm is employed to achieve an efficient distribution of materials into this graph. Ant Systems are successfully applied also in control problems. The proposed method provided sustainable torque and suitable shapes for the designed problems. The results show that the mechanism of optimization of the multi-dimensional topology of electromagnetic devices was successfully performed by the proposed method.

3.3.2 Tabu and Cuckoo search

Tabu search proposed by Glover (1986) [57] is based entirely on the methods described above and their direct development. In the immediate environment of our current solution, we are investigating new, better solutions. In Tabu search method we always trying to keep moving, so we always look for the best solution in the environment, even if it is worse than the solution being tested. Since this method has a lot to explore, so we have to keep in mind, we need to select the direction in which the search was going and in which direction it was not yet. This so-called taboo lists that are marked by taboo tabs. Limitations on Taboo Tabs helping to get through the roads already gone by, increasing the search effectiveness. Cuckoo method [58] is a similar optimization method inspired by the breeding behavior of cuckoo species. In this approach the eggs represents the possible solutions and the search is performed by the quality of the eggs, which leads to finding the best solution. The main differences and advantages of the discussed approaches can be found in some of the most interesting publications collected in Table 7.

Table 7. Tabu and Cuckoo search techniques

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Chen et al [59]	2017	Gbest-guided cuckoo search algorithm	optimization of power systems
Wang et al [60]	2018	improved Tabu search algorithm	optimize a hybrid excited generator
Yang et al [61]	2015	improved Tabu search algorithm	performance evaluation of PM motors with typical PM arrangements

Gbest-guided cuckoo search algorithm with the feedback control strategy and constraint domination rule for the security and economic operation of power system is discussed in Chen et al (2017) [59]. Results of the proposed method were compared with results of another methods developed by researchers in this field. The comparison results indicate that the proposed approach could provide high-quality feasible solutions for different problems.

Paper Wang et al (2018) [60] proposes a hybrid excited generator for variable-speed wind power generation systems. The excitation sources are PMs on the rotor and the field windings on the stator. The proposed generator can achieve constant voltage control and maximum power point tracking control by controlling the field current while the optimization is carried out by a modified Tabu search method. In Yang et al (2015) [61] a new topological design of PM motor is investigated via five different types of permanent magnet arrangements. An improved Tabu search algorithm and finite element method is proposed for the evaluation of the performance of these motors.

3.3.3 SA

SA method has been proposed by Kirkpatrick, Gelatt and Vecchi in 1983 [62]. The SA searches the new solution in a vicinity of a randomly chosen initial solution. But if certain probability conditions are met, it also allows the solution to deteriorate. Therefore, it can escape from a local optimum that a gradient-based or a hill climbing type algorithm cannot. In the iteratively improving methods, a series of random points is generated while in the target function improvement can be observed. To apply the SA strategy, it is necessary to define the following four main elements for each optimization problem; a) Solution Space, b) Transition (i.e., how to generate a new random point), c) Fitness function, d) Annealing Schedule (i.e., determination of the number of iterations to be performed in the internal cycle and the method used to reduce the control parameter in the outer cycle). One of the advantages of the algorithm is that it can be easily implemented. Furthermore, the SA algorithm with proper parameterization does not stuck in a local optimum.

Table 8. Simulated Annealing

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Chiu et al [63]	2016	SA	optimization space-constrained base-vibration system excited with a specific frequency
Farhani et al [64]	2017	SA	real time efficiency optimization of the direct vector-controlled induction motor drives
Torrent-Fontbona and López [65]	2016	SA	DGs

SA is an efficient tool for various optimization problems. It is shown by Chiu et al (2016) [63]; that SA can be applied in the optimization task of space-constrained base-vibration systems. Based on results, in case of increasing the base-vibrating frequency the extracted electrical energy will increase. Consequently, based on the buckling and fatigue analysis, the employed approach for an optimal designed one-mass vibration-based electromagnetic energy harvester is quite efficient in maximizing the energy.

Simulated Annealing algorithm is used for finding a global optimal rotor flux while the suboptimal operating point is determined by a fast analytical method using the induction machine's model in work of Farhani et al (2017) [64]. Paper Torrent-Fontbona and López (2016) [65] reviews the problem and provides a new solution for supporting grid planning with an optimized number DGs. A Particle Swarm optimization method is found to be the tool for finding the optimal number of DGs which allows maximising the profit of the generators, minimizing the system losses and improving the voltage profile.

3.4 Probabilistic reasoning and Bayesian Networks

The core of the theory of "Bayesian" interpretation of probability is based on a concept that probability is a measure of a rational agent's degree of belief in a proposition Ramsey (1926) [66], and

de Finetti (1937)[67]. Probabilistic reasoning with graphical models, known as Bayesian networks or belief networks, has become an active field of research and practice in artificial intelligence, operations research, and statistics in the last two decades. In order to reduce the computational needs asymptotic approximation could be applied but it reduces the precision level. Therefore, Bayesian-type methods are mostly applied in power system and network analysis as it can be seen from Table 9. Few examples can be found for diagnostics problems or parameter estimation problems of power systems using Bayesian techniques.

Table 9. Application of probabilistic reasoning in the field of electrical machines and power systems

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Kari [68]	2018	ANFIS and Dempster-Schafer	fault detection of power transformers through dissolved gas analysis
Kazemdehdashti [69]	2018	density estimator based on generalized cross-entropy method	optimal power flow problem in networks containing renewable energy resources, nonstationary loads
Rubanenko	2017	Probability theory methods and neuro-fuzzy modeling	networks containing renewable energy sources

DGA approach is the basic tool for fault detection of power transformers. Kari (2018) [68] introduces an ANFIS system for this purposes. The outputs of the ANFIS model is evaluated by the Dempster – Schafer method which is originally developed for medical reasoning problems. The results of consistency, accuracy and reliability have been presented in Fig. 18. As is clear, the proposed method has the highest average consistency, accuracy and reliability.

Fig. 18. Results for the study by Kari (2018) [68]

Kazemdehdashti (2018) [69] introduces a new density estimator for optimal power flow problem of networks containing renewable energy sources, etc., using generalized cross-entropy method. Fig. 18 presents the results of study in terms of RMSE (a) and time (b) for comparing the proposed method with diffusion and TPEM techniques for TMV of 14-Bus. As is clear, the RMSE of the proposed method is lower than that for the other methods but this has increased the processing time. TPEM has the lower processing time and the lower accuracy.

Fig. 19. Results for the study by Kazemdehdashti (2018) [69] in terms of RMSE (a) and time (b)

Table 10. Application of Bayesian methods in the field of electrical machines and power systems

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Jiang et al [70]	2015	Bayesian inference method	diagnostics of a CCGT power plant
Lakehal et al [71]	2017	Bayesian network based on the Duval triangle method	Transformer condition monitoring via Dissolved gas analysis
Mansouri et al [72]	2015	Bayesian methods	state and parameter estimation of IMs

Paper Jiang et al (2015) [70] presents an integrated Bayesian probabilistic method for precise power splitting and the degradation diagnostics of a single-shaft combined cycle plant, accounting for uncertainties in the measured data. Lakehal et al (2017) [71] introduces a Bayesian network based on the Duval triangle method in the dissolved gas analysis which is the primary technique for identifying faults in transformers. The proposed model makes a quantitative estimation analysis of transformer faults, which supported the IEEE C57.104 standard.

Mansouri et al (2015) [72] applies the Bayes method in nonlinear time-varying state and parameter estimation task of induction machines (IMs). Based on results, the PF method has a higher accuracy compared that for the EKF and UKF. Also, IPF improves the PF, significantly. Based on the results of

the second comparative study, for all methods, estimation accuracy depends on estimating the model parameters as well as the convergence of the estimated parameters and states.

3.5 Hybrid soft computing methods

Single SC techniques are found to be efficient due to their robustness and easy interpretability. At the same, though their usage can be so advantageous, it is still limited by their exponentially increasing computational complexity. The combination of different techniques offers the synergy of their beneficial properties. Consequently, hybrid soft computing techniques have gained popularity.

Table 11. Application of Hybrid methods in the field of electrical machines and power systems

Reference	Year	Technique	Application
Dai et al [73]	2016	quantum-behaved particle swarm optimization for parameter identification with SA	ensure the accuracy of the DFIG and improve the control performance of the generator
McDonald [74]	2017	hybrid genetic algorithm and pattern search process	optimize direct drive permanent magnet synchronous generators for offshore direct drive wind turbines
Meo [75]	2016	combining a multi-objective particle swarm optimization and artificial neural network	design optimization of a direct-drive permanent magnet flux switching generators for low power wind applications

Dai et al (2016) [73] proposes a new hybrid quantum-behaved particle swarm optimization – based solution for improving the precision of parameter identification (five parameters including stator resistance, stator inductance, rotor resistance, rotor inductance, and mutual inductance of stator and rotor) of the doubly-fed wind power generator (DFIG). Results indicated that the proposed algorithm accelerated the computing process by reducing the processing time. For the optimization of direct drive permanent magnet synchronous generators McDonald, (2017) [74] used a hybrid genetic algorithm and pattern search process and has found that the surface-mounted permanent magnet generator produces the lower cost of energy.

With the purpose of reducing the costs and weight of the machine while maximizing the amplitude of the induced voltage as well as minimizing its total harmonic distortion Meo, (2016) [75] has presented a new hybrid approach for the design optimization of a direct-drive permanent magnet flux switching generators. Fig. 19 presents results of AHP, NSGA-II, abyss and proposed ANN-SMPSO in terms of Cost (a), THD (b), Weight (c) and em (d). As is clear from Fig. 19, the proposed method reduces the cost (\$) about 23.85 %, reduces the THD about 17 %, reduces the weight about 44.73% and increases em about 2.6 %. These values claim that the proposed hybrid method improves the condition compared with that for the other techniques.

Fig. 20. Results for the study by Meo (2016) [75] in terms of Cost (a), THD (b), Weight (c) and em (d)

In general, it can be claimed that hybrid methods can be the most successful methods than single methods. Because these methods can take advantage of several methods simultaneously and reduce the defects in each method. With the advancement of artificial intelligence and soft computing methods, the trend towards hybrid methods increases for the reasons given. There are still many hybrid methods that have not been used, which suggests that exploration of these methods be increased which can clarify the dark points in this and increase the orientation and usage by the researchers.

4. Discussions

The trend of recent years suggests that the greatest flexibility of design may be ensured by soft computing tools. In this paper we explore the latest techniques of intelligent algorithmic methods for design and control of electrical machines and investigate how the reviewed methods affect the solution.

The great majority of *automated control* tasks needs an existence of the system model on some level. General practice of the simple feedback control applies the a priori knowledge, i.e. the system is regulated by the variation of the measured output. However, in practice the system under control is highly nonlinear, only few variables are measurable external disturbances degrade the performance and also the technological processes generate further constraints in the desired control of the system dynamics [76]. In addition, the adaptive and advanced control methods usually apply the mathematically complicated Lyapunov method [77, 78]. It is clear that the system modeling and mathematically easy manageability provided by advanced methods are the key factors in a successful control method design [12]. The choice of the proper control law in case of a specific electric machine and drive system raises many questions. Below we make an attempt to highlight in

how the replacement of conventional techniques with the various „soft“ approaches collected in this paper may allow the greatest benefits.

The algorithmic approaches rely on the physical system equations of motion described by mathematical equations. Such techniques calculate analytically for example the controllers parameters. In such cases when information may be incomplete or the system model is not fully available fuzzy logic can be applied as universal approximator due to the linguistic terms. It is suitable for modelling the system behaviour, deducing the control law by fuzzy reasoning built on implications or tuning the parameters by applying the suitable membership functions. Furthermore, the various fuzzy operators allow the flexible fitting the model behaviour to the real scenario. Engineers usually face regression tasks during the control design process. The regression in practice is related to measured data. For each measurement an error value should be assigned that the classical regression cannot handle in common models. In spite of this, the fuzzy regression assigns the error values to the measurement error and if the regression line is within this error range that line is accepted. However, an infinite number of lines with such properties may exist within the error range. Therefore, by applying fuzzy membership function which follow the error probability's distribution and setting a rule basis could easily solve this problem without large computational burdens.

Potential advantage of fuzzy logic based approximation is that they allow to optimize multiple variants and configurations and reduce complexity, so the problem may have limited to a smaller number of parameters. Furthermore, the linguistic variables ensure great flexibility context-sensitive machine modeling. This will allow the system to learn by example. We can construct rules whose results are as close as possible for the expected results.

Additionally, the classical control methods require the immediate response of the system in various situation depending on the environment's reactions. Fuzzy control allows to take into account not just the physical properties but also the rules that cannot be exactly mathematically described. A real situation would require a large number of parameters that cannot be totally measured under the operation conditions, for instance if we wish to teach an electric car how to behave in specific traffic situations. Such cases demand immediate responses and we cannot wait minutes while the on-board computer solves complicated differential equations. Since the application of fuzzy logic and other soft computing tools allow the system to learn from examples. After the proper rule system is set up, the system can give the nearly ideal responses.

It is obvious, when only approximate system model is available, heuristic or cognitive techniques can be applied which describe the context- or situation dependent behavior of the system.

The Neural Networks emerging from statistical methods are capable for approximating regular function [79]. This property is highly advantageous in nonlinear control problems where analytically unknown nonlinear functions are required to be found using only few (measurement) data. Today a significant number of the NN variants are known therefore specific and highly nonlinear cases can be efficiently handled. We should emphasize, that both NN and Fuzzy methods can be adapted in most of the conventional control and system modeling techniques.

The estimation of the physical parameters which characterize the model of the machine is also essential for the efficient control of electrical machines. Parameter estimation is particularly fundamental in condition monitoring tasks. Here, the parameter estimation techniques are similar to the methods applied in the control law syntheses and state observations. Such tasks mainly result in nonlinear programming problems where the previous knowledge may become crucial. Since, the Bayesian statistic may enhance the estimation performance in contrast to classical probabilistic solutions. Examples can be found, e.g. in [80] and in the publications mentioned in Section 3.4. Furthermore, an important step of the estimation is its convergence. The resulted optimization problems may have many constraints. At this point, the evolutionary computing techniques, for instance the heuristic search methods are applicable, such as Genetic Algorithms, Taboo Search, Cuckoo method, etc.

Optimization issues arise in most of engineering disciplines and we encounter with them in our everyday life. The optimization task aims achieving the best possible solution according to some objective function by setting the appropriate values of the decision variables. Finding the optimal

solution is typically a difficult task, because in practice, the target function is nonlinear, different constraints may occur, etc., and often the algorithm stuck into a local extrema of the search space. In case of electrical machine design, although the general practice gives the main directions [4], but all of the modeling assumptions are necessary to be satisfied from the beginning of the design process [81]. Since, design optimization may dispute further questions. Constrained multivariate optimization problems usually arise during *machine design issues* from which it follows that the mathematical models become more complicated.

The classical design practice can describe the problems only with complicated differential equations. Of course, the parameters must be known to solve the equations. Usually, it would take a lot of parameters to describe a real system, or it would take too long time to solve the problem. The parameters in most cases otherwise cannot be measured, it is therefore necessary to estimate them. Another solution is soft computing, especially fuzzy logic.

The general feature of designing technical systems is that the same task can be solved in several ways [82]. Comparison of individual solutions is rather subjective, weighting the advantages and disadvantages relative to each other basically influences the assessment. The solution that is considered to be optimal can only be selected on the basis of a pre-formulated criteria system. The subjectivity of judgment is carried by the accepted criteria system. Since, its adoption, the optimum system selection has become a specific task. We should be aware that one solution that is considered to be optimal by one of the criteria systems, using another set of criteria, is no longer optimal. Fuzzy logic is proven to be suitable in such assessments. The optimal solution may depend on the applied model parameters. Therefore, once the optimal model has been set up a post-optimality analysis should be performed, usually referred to as parametric study. The role of sensitivity analysis is revealing the sensitive parameters. Classical techniques of sensitivity analyses are observing the influence of the perturbation of the parameters. Soft computing tools could support also this step of the process by providing soft boundaries of the sets.

We see, that finding a single optimum solution can be a major challenge. However, finding several optimal solutions at once may result in a more complex task. The so-called multi-modal optimization (MMO) approach serves as solution of these latter optimization problems [83] during machine design process. Multimodal optimization could benefit from the various evolutionary-based methods, for instance in founding the basin of attraction of the optimum, reducing the search domain. In addition, the above chapters give insight in modern heuristics which may speed up the design process with combination of classical optimization because they allowing easy parallelization and system level optimization. Similarly, the fulfilment of the various conditions of the model configurations at the same time is problematic and requires skillful designers. Multi-model optimization (MMO) performs the design process by optimizing multiple models having some shared variables. The multi-model optimization approach uses different representations including coarser and more detailed models and allows the multiple configurations [83]. Therefore, in these cases, stochastic searching methods play a prominent role. Many studies suggest various evolutionary algorithms to multimodal problems (see, eg. [84])

However, the expected improvement depends on many conditions, of which the most prominent may be the performance. Most of the suggested algorithmic techniques are only partially effective or applicable to a specific class of problems without capability of simultaneous satisfying all the different requirements. Further investigations are needed to achieve more reliable and general methods. The theory of fuzzy logic has been elaborated and well established by today, but its introduction into new areas is still ongoing. From the above presented general panorama of the literature, it is obvious that there are only few results on the global optimization solutions of evolutionary techniques and there is still limited contribution for its fundamental theory. Altogether, these observations suggest that by transferring the approaches between intelligent computational methods in the direction of MMO approaches could be an excellent step toward new and effective algorithmic techniques and a well-founded theory.

5. Conclusions

Electrical machines and drive systems account for about 46 % of all global electricity used in power industries, where two-thirds of this is consumed by electric motors. There is a clear global demand for a comprehensive design methodology to support these new applications and satisfy power efficiency requirements. Current trend of global industrial automation, the application of electric drive systems (including power electronics and drive control) is expected to grow rapidly in the next decade. These achievements raise the need of the control strategy and machine design techniques to evolve rapidly to the newly created drive conditions and adapt to the overall systems performance requirements.

Several computation approaches are available to improve the machine performance through design and control, including classical closed-form analytical analysis, lumped parameter models based on the determination of detailed parameters from finite element analysis, and nonlinear time-domain finite element analysis. Most of the issues of each design and control steps is covered by advanced methods. A wide range of intelligent computational techniques serves for the designers and all of them has advantages and disadvantages. Selecting the best method may not be straightforward because it requires the user to understand the differences among the computation algorithms. This brief literature survey clearly indicates that the fundamental issue is finding the trade-off among model complexity, accuracy, and computing time. Designers could use a combination of various Soft Computing techniques as the optimal solution to obtain the required machine performances as hybrid techniques.

Recent studies have provided from theoretical point of view how modern heuristics and soft computing techniques may improve the efficiency of engineering practice in the field of electrical machine design and control. Due the problem-specific nature of SC methods, new effective algorithmic techniques necessary to be designed for implementing them in any stage of the process. Potential advantages of SC relying in the capabilities to deal with context-sensitivity, high flexibility in spite of classical methods based on sharp borders. Additionally, without complex mathematical operations, sorting can be automatically performed on alternatives. In addition, the relationships between categories can be easily examined.

At the present time here is still no general theory or methodology for designing such heuristics, e.g. neural network, genetic algorithms, etc. The primary intention of the designer should be the specification of the structure of the neural network or of the fuzzy reasoning system, etc. After, the key parameters must be identified. Experimental results may help training these systems. Our review support that the hybrid methods outperform the standard ones. Considerable progress in the field could achieved by the synergetic utilization of the heuristic algorithmic and MMO methods. Our research could possibly support designers finding enhanced methods.

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